

РАЗДЕЛ. ГУМАНИТАРНЫЕ НАУКИ

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**SPOKEN ENGLISH IN PUBLIC SCHOOLS IN RUSSIA
OR WHAT'S WRONG WITH THEM?**

M.V. Koryakin,

Candidate of pedagogical sciences, Leading Researcher, Department for the
Study of Reading Problems,
FSBI of Science Scientific and Publishing Centre "NAUKA" of the
Russian Academy of Sciences,
Moscow

Annotation: The aim of the article is to take a look at the problems of mastering spoken English in modern public schools in Russia. The main trends in the study of English as the language of international communication are considered. Special attention is paid to the methods, educational materials designed to successfully learn English.

Keywords: state education institutions in Russia, methodology, specifics, educational materials and features of mastering English as the language of international communication, technical base of the school for learning foreign languages

The studies [1-7, and others] of learning foreign languages problems in the USSR and modern Russia give grounds to draw a disappointing conclusion that the worst system of teaching spoken English in our country has developed in public schools. It is in schools children start getting acquainted with a foreign language in the 2nd or even in the 1st grade, and "learn" it 8-11 years. It's known that in the Soviet Union languages (mainly German, English, French, and rarely – Spanish) began studying in the 5th or in the 3-rd grade. And it's impossible to confidently say foreign languages were taught better in public schools at that time. For example, after the Great Patriotic War (The World War II) soviet public schools had some problems with the German language as it was the

language of our enemy. Therefore, children refused to learn it. Later English became number one among foreign languages and began to be started to learn as the language of our rival in the arms race and the "cold war". However, there are big problems with learning languages in our country. Now we are living in the 3rd decade of the XXI century, and it would seem that everything that could have changed in our schools has already changed: textbooks, teachers (the amount of old Soviet school teachers is not many), classrooms became computerized, but we can see the soviet schoolchildren were not able to master spoken foreign languages quite well, and current students cannot speak in English either. By the way, when I was in school I was learning German but couldn't speak it, and neither all my classmates, and everyone I knew. So, the author of the article "Why we don't speak a foreign language fluently after school" notes that "with all the abundance of approaches that appeared in the XXI century, our school programmes are based on the most outdated and most inefficient approach..." [8]. After all, every year our schoolchildren take the State Exam which has such an item as "speaking" – but why they don't know how to speak English? Which begs the question: why public schools in Russia can't educate schoolchildren spoken English? What's wrong with our schools or teachers? Or maybe something wrong with children? The answer, it may seem, lies in plain sight: the problem is not with the schoolchildren or teachers, they are OK, I hope. In general, from my perspective, the problem lies in the school education system itself and in the fact that we are all outside the English-speaking environment. Besides, today's school textbooks materials are although modern, but still based on the grammar-translation method (when there are more progressive teaching methods), which goes with its roots to the middle ages. Meanwhile, against the background of articulation / phonetics / melody of the language, such important aspects as phrases and merging of sounds are completely ignored. It should be emphasized that for native English speakers, expressions are much more important than grammar though they actively use more grammatical rules and phrases / expressions than non-native once do, while our schools often-times focus on grammar. Also, a very important nuance remains outside the scope of attention: the English language is constantly changing, undergoing serious transformations. Furthermore, the school textbooks are used that were written 5-10 years ago. Many of us know English has got different accents (British, American, Canadian,

Australian, New Zealand, Indian, etc.) and some pronunciation variants of words / expressions – taking into account place of living and dialects. That some words and phrases leave oral speech and writing, they are replaced by other forms, phrases, expressions, idioms, slang. It's no secret in the 9th grade, a school student must have a level not lower than A2 (Elementary), in the 11th grade – not lower than B1 (Intermediate) – according to the pan-European scale of foreign language proficiency (CEFR): from A1 (Beginner) to C2 (Proficiency). In real life, few school students are able to communicate at A2 level (on social topics: home, work, studying, travelling, national cuisine, lifestyle, hobbies, etc.) and even more so, at B1 level (the ability more to confidently socialize with native speakers). Consequently, the majority of applicants entering various colleges and universities of the country with 80+ scores for the Unified State Exam (the English language), as a rule, are not able to speak in English at the level of not only B1, but also A2 – unless they were additionally engaged with highly qualified specialists: in language schools, with a tutor or at professional courses. Actually, they can read more or less well, translate texts into Russian (but from Russian into English – it's a huge problem for most of them), they know grammar and take tests, have a decent vocabulary, they are not good at spoken English, because it is a very special skill that is achieved through many years of practice. In fact, HOW you can master a spoken language if it is not actually practised in public schools and that is called speaking it's a parody of speech: as if you were constantly speaking by syllables. It should be recognized it's not enough to simply fill the words into gaps in sentences or complete texts with the verbs or take written tests for vocabulary knowledge – this does not give much. It's much more important to develop listening skills – listening comprehension of non-adapted speech of native English speakers using their patterns of speaking.

In my view, in common, such an uncertain command of English (first of all, *speaking*) is expressed in a number of reasons: 1) very low motivation of most schoolchildren to learn any foreign language; 2) *the grammar-translation method* used in secondary schools absolutely does not allow to master either spoken or written language at a high level; 3) in our education institutions students are mainly taught THEORY of the language; 4) 2-3 lessons a week (up to 2 hours) – that's an extremely limited amount of time to practise conversational skills: discussions on social and other

topics in the language being studied; 5) not many practical lessons (or there are none at all) for listening comprehension skills; 6) not taken into account the fact that written and spoken English have a number of significant differences *in terms of spelling and pronunciation*; 7) not taken into account that native English speakers use reducing, abbreviations, phrasal verbs, slang, idioms in their speech, because *English is an idiomatic language*; 8) a weak technical base in the classrooms which would allow to actively develop listening and speaking skills; 9) the level of experience of the majority of school teachers (with all due respect) leaves something to be desired – against the background of low salary and incredibly high hourly workload in public schools; 10) probably, there is a low interest of most school teachers to train children a foreign spoken language.

In this regard, I would like to draw the attention of specialists, teachers, methods, linguists and everyone connected with foreign languages to the fact that *the current system of teaching spoken English* (I can admit that the situation with other languages is better) *simply does not work in Russian state schools*. Therefore, it's necessary to seriously change, adjust, and improve this field of activity, reaching a decent level of proficiency in spoken English nationwide. Here many may ask the question: *why do we need this at all?* Well, we “learn” the language at school 10-11 years, then in college, university for another 4-6 years, well, *we don't know how to speak it – but are we still ready to continue to do that in the same way?* Most likely if we are really wishing (not be pretending) to have a good command of spoken English, *we should accept the fact of a weak and ineffective system of learning spoken English in our non-specialized education institutions*. This is especially important, since the study time in schools, and then in colleges, universities, is spent on learning a “dead” language. It is as if we were communicating in Latin (or Esperanto), where Latin, although widely used today in such spheres as medicine, biology, pharmacology, law, philosophy, *but it is not the language of international communication like English is*. Consequently, the situation could be radically corrected by the ADOPTED IMPROVED NATIONWIDE TRAINING PROGRAMME *based on the communicative method* of language acquisition, which should be accompanied by well-thought-out, practical materials that make it possible to effectively master spoken English in public schools. *It is also necessary to increase a number of practical classes, and lessons (ideally daily lessons) should be conducted*

exclusively in English, actively using interactive speaking – to fully immerse in the world of the language being studied.

I think more interesting student's books / workbooks for schoolchildren of different age groups could act as effective tools, according to which you can successfully study and master English. For example, for primary school students, it could be a series of student's books "*Family and Friends*" from **Oxford University Press** (7 levels of difficulty), which is accompanied by a "*Grammar Friends*" book – it contains grammar tasks for different levels of English language proficiency. This could be a series of books "*Fly High*" published by **Pearson Longman** – it consists of 8 levels of difficulty: from elementary (A1) to professional (C2). It could be the textbooks "*English File*" or "*Headway*" / "*New Headway*" (from A0 to C1) – also published by **Oxford University Press** – they would be suitable for teaching middle and high school students. The advantage of this series of textbooks is that they are built on a *communicative teaching method* where *4 basic language skills are equally worked out: speaking, listening, reading, and writing*. The benefits of other textbooks for the successful mastery of the English language can be found in this link [9]. Actually, it's possible to learn from the existing textbooks in schools, focusing on *the improvement of listening skills, speaking, writing, reading aloud, and retelling* which is the basis of the thought process. Ultimately, *these skills can allow you to overcome the psychological barrier of expressing thoughts in a non-native language*. To be honest, and it needs to be highlighted, *speaking English is a SKILL which should be formed*. It's like learning to play the piano, to be able to drive a car, ride a bike or to fly a plane.

Summing up, I would like to note that we can't afford to ignore the experience of non-English-speaking countries, where foreign languages, including English, begin to be studied at preschool age or in elementary school, in fact, like in Russia. The only difference is that education institutions do not burden children with complex grammatical constructions, but try to instill interest in a foreign language in a playful way and from the first years of training they teach them to actively express their thoughts and feelings in a language that is not native to them. The point is when there is already a good base of a language, it's easier to improve and develop it in the future – when studying at college, university and then in professional activities. Why, in my view, schoolchildren should

practise English at school daily and independently out of it because any language has to be learned **COMPREHENSIVELY** – *it must be started with speaking like we do it in our native language*. Unfortunately, good knowledge of English among our schoolchildren and the ability to speaking it that is not a mass of nature. In this context raises a rhetorical question: whether our public schools have a goal of teaching spoken English at all?

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